

EFFECT OF HUMAN HAIR FIBER ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CONCRETE

Annotation:

Over the years, materials such as steel, jute, and wood have been commonly used for reinforcing concrete structures, enhancing their stability and mechanical properties. However, with the increasing demand for infrastructure due to population growth, there has been a corresponding rise in concrete production, leading to concerns about environmental degradation and waste accumulation. To address these issues, researchers have been exploring the use of waste materials as substitutes for traditional concrete constituents, aiming to mitigate construction pollution and reduce landfill waste. One innovative approach involves incorporating waste Human Hair Fiber (HHF) into concrete fabrication, contributing to sustainable construction practices. This study investigates the impact of HHF reinforcement on concrete strength, considering human hair lengths of 20, 50, and 80 mm at varying addition rates of 1%, 1.5%, and 2% by the weight of cement. The results indicate that a 1.5% addition of human hair, particularly lengths of 50 mm and 80 mm, demonstrates optimal compressive and flexural strength, while a 1% addition of 50 mm human hair exhibits the highest tensile strength at 28 days.

Keywords:

Human hair, Mortar, Fiber reinforcement, Sustainability, Mechanical properties.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Concrete is a brittle material that exhibits strength primarily in compression but is weak in tension. To address this limitation, Fiber Reinforced Concrete (FRC) has emerged as a solution, involving the incorporation of various types of fibers to enhance the mechanical properties of concrete structures [1]. Historically, fibers such as steel, glass, and polymeric fibers have been used as reinforcement in concrete, with the aim of reducing cracking and improving overall performance [2]. Additionally, natural fibers like horse hair, straw, coir, sisal, jute, and bamboo have been utilized in ancient constructions as reinforcement materials [3].

While steel fibers have been widely adopted due to their availability and strengthening properties,

concerns such as corrosion, low workability, and limited crack relief have prompted researchers to explore alternative fiber materials [4]. Wood fibers, derived from processed pine scraps, have been employed in autoclaved aerated concrete, albeit with high maintenance costs and water retention properties [7]. Similarly, plant fibers have been investigated, although their hydrophilic nature and high water absorption present challenges in cement compatibility [8].

In recent years, human hair fiber (HHF) has garnered attention as a potential reinforcement material for concrete. Human hair, a non-biodegradable waste product, poses environmental challenges when disposed of improperly. However, utilizing it as a fiber reinforcement in concrete offers a sustainable solution to this problem [9], [10]. HHF exhibits high flexibility comparable to copper wire and can effectively strengthen and protect mortar from spalling [11].

Research on Human Hair Fiber Concrete (HHFC) has demonstrated promising results in improving various properties of concrete. Adding HHF has been shown to enhance compressive strength, alkali resistance, water permeability, and durability of concrete structures [9]. Studies have indicated significant improvements in compressive strength with HHF additions, with a 20.22% increment observed in M25 concrete compared to M15 and M20 mixes [9]. Furthermore, the incorporation of HHF has shown potential in making concrete structures corrosion-resistant and lightweight, thus aiding in seismic resistance [12].

Optimizing the concentration and length of HHF in concrete mixes is crucial for achieving desired mechanical properties. Response surface methodology (RSM) has been employed to determine the optimal concentration of HHF, with findings suggesting that a concentration of 3.2% by volume and a hair strand length of 0.752 inches result in optimal concrete strength [13]. Additionally, studies have reported increases in impact strength, tensile stress, and elongation at break with the addition of HHF, highlighting its potential to improve the overall performance of concrete [16], [17].

Comparative studies have also been conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of HHF against other fiber materials. Research comparing HHF with wave polypropylene fibers revealed that HHF exhibited superior strength characteristics, albeit with a reduction in concrete fluidity [18], [19]. These findings underscore the potential of HHF as a cost-effective and sustainable alternative for reinforcing concrete structures.

Figure 1: Schematic of hair fiber structure

The present study aims to further explore the utilization of HHF as concrete reinforcement to enhance mechanical properties. Tests will be conducted on concrete specimens with varying percentages of HHF and different lengths of human hair fibers. By systematically evaluating the effects of HHF on properties such as compressive strength, tensile strength, flexural strength, and durability, the study aims to provide insights into the optimal use of HHF in concrete fabrication.

The utilization of HHF in concrete offers a promising avenue for enhancing the mechanical properties and sustainability of concrete structures. By repurposing a non-biodegradable waste material, HHF not only addresses environmental concerns but also contributes to the development of durable and resilient infrastructure. Through systematic research and optimization, HHF has the potential to revolutionize the field of concrete reinforcement, offering a viable and eco-friendly alternative to traditional fiber materials.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Following are the objectives of this work:

- Evaluate the mechanical strength: Assess the tensile, compressive, and flexural strengths of concrete specimens reinforced with varying percentages of human hair fiber.
- Analyze performance factors: Investigate the impact resistance, modulus of elasticity, workability, adhesion properties, and long-term durability of concrete containing human hair fiber.
- Assess feasibility and sustainability: Examine the cost-effectiveness and sustainability aspects of using human hair as a reinforcement material in concrete and compare its mechanical properties with industry-standard concrete for construction applications.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Numerous research studies have delved into the incorporation of human hair as a fiber reinforcement in concrete, aiming to enhance the mechanical properties of concrete structures while addressing environmental concerns associated with waste disposal. These investigations have explored various aspects of utilizing human hair fibers to improve concrete performance, including the length and percentage of fibers added to the mix, as well as the type and grade of cement used. Findings from these studies have consistently demonstrated that incorporating human hair fibers in concrete leads to improvements in tensile strength, compressive strength, flexural strength, impact resistance, and durability compared to conventional concrete mixes.

Researchers have conducted experiments to assess the impact of reinforcing concrete structures with human hair fibers (HHF) on the mechanical properties of the concrete matrix. Results have indicated a significant increase in compressive, flexural, and splitting tensile strength as the percentage of HHF added to the mixture by weight of cement is increased. However, variations in curing times for concrete specimens have been observed as HHF content increases, with a decline in compressive strength compared to improvements in splitting tensile and flexural strength. Nonetheless, the study has demonstrated that HHF can reduce cracking patterns and enhance the mechanical properties of concrete structures.

Studies have also investigated the utilization of human hair waste as a reinforcing material in fiber-reinforced concrete, resulting in significant improvements in various concrete properties. As the percentage of hair fibers added to the concrete increases, there is a remarkable increase in the concrete's properties, including higher compressive strength and better split tensile strength compared to conventional concrete. The incorporation of hair fibers has been found to reduce crack formation and propagation, making it suitable for seismic-resistant constructions.

Furthermore, experiments have explored the effectiveness of different sizes of human hair fibers in enhancing the properties of concrete. Results have shown that the addition of 10mm hair fibers led to increased compressive strength compared to 50mm fibers, indicating their greater efficiency in withstanding loads. However, the study highlighted the potential of both fiber sizes in improving concrete properties and controlling cracking.

In addition, investigations have evaluated the effect of adding different percentages of HHF to concrete on compressive strength and split tensile strength. The results have indicated that the maximum

compressive strength is achieved with 1.5% HHF, which is higher than the strength of normal concrete. Moreover, concrete made with 1.5% HHF exhibited higher split tensile strength compared to lower percentages of HHF, highlighting the potential of HHF as a reinforcing material in concrete applications.

Overall, these studies underscore the potential of utilizing human hair waste as a sustainable reinforcement material in concrete, contributing to waste reduction and improved concrete performance. The findings provide valuable insights into optimizing concrete mix designs and developing environmentally friendly construction materials.

4. METHODOLOGY

To evaluate mechanical strength entails assessing the tensile, compressive, and flexural strengths of concrete specimens reinforced with different proportions of human hair fiber. This process involves several essential stages:

- ✓ Literature Review
- ✓ Material Selection
- ✓ Specimen Preparation
- ✓ High-Temperature Exposure Setup
- ✓ Temperature Exposure Regimen
- ✓ Testing Procedures
- ✓ Data Collection and Analysis
- ✓ Statistical Analysis
- ✓ Documentation and Reporting
- ✓ Quality Control
- ✓ Recommendations for Future Research

5. TESTING RESULT

Figure 2: Mechanical properties of nominal concrete (M25)

Figure 3: Compressive quality of concrete with 20 mm HHF

Figure 4: Compressive quality of concrete with 50 mm HHF

Figure 5: Compressive quality of concrete with 80 mm HHF

Figure 6: Compressive quality comparison of normal mix and concrete with HHF of different lengths

Figure 7: Split tensile characteristics of concrete with 20 mm HHF

Figure 8: Split tensile characteristics of concrete with 50 mm HHF

Figure 9: Split tensile characteristics of concrete with 80 mm HHF

Figure 10: Split tensile characteristics comparison of normal mix and concrete with HHF of different lengths

6. CONCLUSION

The escalating ecological impact of non-biodegradable waste production, including human hair, has prompted research into its potential reuse as fiber reinforcement in concrete. This study compared normal M25 grade concrete with variations incorporating Human Hair Fiber (HHF) at different lengths and percentages. The findings indicate that concrete with 1.5% HHF of 50 mm length exhibits optimal compressive strength, representing a substantial improvement over conventional concrete. Impact strength increases by approximately 40% up to 1.5% HHF addition across all lengths, although a decline is observed at 2% HHF. Similarly, split tensile strength peaks at 1% HHF of 50 mm length, showing a notable 21% increase compared to control concrete. Bending strength also improves with HHF incorporation, with a 25% increase observed at 1.5% HHF of 80 mm length. Overall, adding 1.5% to 2% HHF of 50 to 80 mm length significantly enhances concrete performance compared to traditional mixes, offering ecological benefits, cost efficiency, and improved stability.

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